

NITROGEN FIXATION AND TOTAL BACTERIAL COUNT ON THE APPLICATION OF ENERGY MATERIALS TO ALKALI SOILS.

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Nitrogen fixation in alkali soils on the addition of energy materials like carbohydrates has been studied. As in the case of normal soils, nitrogen fixation takes place in the alkali soils and it is always greater in the soils exposed to sunlight than in those kept covered although the total bacterial numbers are smaller in the former than in the latter. The nitrogen fixed per g. of carbon oxidised is greater in the soils exposed to light than in the covered ones and the order of fixation is more or less the same as that obtained with normal soils.

There are vast tracts of alkali soils in different parts of India. It is estimated that the total area of alkali land (*Usar*) in the United Province alone is over five millions of acres. The chief defects of such a soil have already been reported in an earlier communication (Dhar, *J. Indian Chem. Soc. Ind. & News Ed.*, 1939, 2, 105). The following results show the difference between a normal soil and an alkali soil.

TABLE I.

	Total nitrogen.	Total carbon.	μ .	Total bacteria in millions per g. of dry soil.
Alkali soil collected from Bani near Allahabad	0.0336 %	0.2301 %	10.5	0.12
Normal soil Allahabad	0.0516	0.5304	7.8	13.3

The object of this investigation is to ascertain whether nitrogen fixation takes place in the alkali soils, as in the case of normal soils, when treated with carbohydrates. The experiments were carried on with soil collected from Bani (near Allahabad). The carbohydrates used were chemically pure, canesugar, glucose and fructose.

E. X P E R I M E N T A L.

The alkali soil (1 kg.) was mixed thoroughly with each of the above-mentioned energy materials (29 g.) and 250 c.c. of water in enamelled basins (diameter 26 cm.). The experiments were carried out in duplicate. Control

experiments were also performed with alkali soils without the addition of carbohydrates. One set of basins was exposed to sunlight daily for eight hours and the other corresponding set, covered loosely with a double layer of thick black cloth to exclude light, was also kept side by side along with the exposed basins to eliminate the temperature effect. Water (160 c.c.) was added twice a day to the exposed soils and once to the soils covered to maintain a uniform moisture content. Before commencement of the experiments estimations of total nitrogen, total carbon and total bacterial numbers of the original soil were made. At regular intervals the total nitrogen, total carbon and total bacterial numbers of the exposed and covered soils were determined simultaneously. The following results are the mean of the duplicate experiments.

TABLE II.

1 Kg. of soil + 20 g. of canesugar.

Date.	Exposed.			Covered.		
	Total N.	Total C.	Total bacteria.*	Total N.	Total C.	Total bacteria.*
29-12-1937 Original soil	0.0336%	0.2301%	0.12%	0.0336%	0.2301%	0.12
Immediately after mixing	0.0336	1.0612	—	0.0336	1.0596	—
17-1-38	0.036	0.01612	8.2	0.0348	0.9403	10.3
8-2-38	0.038	0.7066	22.4	0.0364	0.7894	39.5
8-3-38	0.039	0.5318	10.7	0.0364	0.6427	28.4
4-4-38	0.0396	0.432	9.1	0.0364	0.5135	23.6

TABLE III.

1 Kg. of soil + 20 g. of glucose.

Date.	Exposed.			Covered.		
	Total N.	Total C.	Total bacteria.*	Total N.	Total C.	Total bacteria.*
29-12-37 Original soil	0.0336%	0.2301%	0.12	0.0336%	0.2301%	0.12
Immediately after mixing	0.0036	1.0214	—	0.0336	1.0286	—
21-1-38	0.036	0.8579	6.2	0.0348	0.8926	7.1
10-2-38	0.0376	0.6849	23.6	0.0356	0.7529	36.8
10-3-38	0.039	0.5411	12.0	0.0356	0.6041	27.5
6-4-38	0.0399	0.419	8.9	0.0366	0.4601	28.8

* (millions/g of dry soil),

Similar results were obtained with fructose. In the control soils without the addition of carbohydrates, there was a slight fall of nitrogen, carbon and bacterial numbers.

The following table shows the amount of nitrogen fixed per gram of carbon oxidised both in alkali and normal soils.

TABLE IV.

	Alkali soil		Normal soil	
	Exposed.	Covered.	Exposed.	Covered.
Cane-sugar	9.5	5.1	—	—
Glucose	9.9	5.2	12.5	6.5
Fructose	11.3	5.6	11.9	6.8

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